

Air pollution induced Osteoporosis: A challenge to keep bones healthy in highly polluted cities

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Abstract

Poor air quality is associated with a higher risk factor for bone fractures and osteoporosis, especially in low-income communities. Osteoporosis is characterized by low bone mass and density. Osteoporosis and bone fractures can be caused by air pollution and found that populations in areas of higher ambient concentrations of particulate matter less than 2.5 μm had lower bone mineral density with higher rates of hospital admissions for bone fractures, which led to the conclusion that air pollution is a risk factor for osteoporosis and bone fractures.

KEYWORDS

Air pollution, bone, effects, fractures, health, osteoporosis

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Air pollution has various health effects. The health of susceptible and sensitive individuals can be impacted even on low air pollution days. Short-term exposure to air pollutants is closely related to COPD (Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease), cough, shortness of breath, wheezing, asthma, respiratory disease, and high rates of hospitalization (a measurement of morbidity). The long-term effects associated with air pollution are chronic asthma, diabetes, pulmonary insufficiency, cardiovascular diseases, and cardiovascular mortality. Moreover, air pollution seems to have various malign health effects in early human life, such as respiratory, cardiovascular, mental, and perinatal disorders, leading to infant mortality or chronic disease in adult age.

Poor air quality is associated with higher risk factor for bone fractures and osteoporosis, especially in low-income communities. Osteoporosis is characterized by low bone mass and density. Osteoporosis and bone fractures can be caused by air pollution, and found that populations in areas of higher ambient concentrations of particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m had lower bone mineral density with higher rates of hospital admissions for bone fractures, which led to the conclusion that air pollution is a risk factor for osteoporosis and bone fractures. [1]

Prada et al. found that air polluted with particulate matter, such as black carbon, is harmful to bone health, although they did not have access to data on other air pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) that Nakao et al. found to have adverse effects on COPD. Nonetheless, another recent study by Chang et al. found that air polluted with greater concentrations of NO₂, along with carbon monoxide, in Taiwan did increase the risk of osteoporosis and bone fractures. [1-3]

The reason why this is significant is because some cities are heavily polluted. Asian Federation of Osteoporosis Societies (AFOS) projected that the number of bone fractures caused by osteoporosis, specifically hip fractures, will increase 2.28-fold within the next few decades in Asia with 1.59-fold increase in health care costs. [1]

Based on the magnitude of the public health impact, it is certain that different kinds of interventions should be taken into account. Success and effectiveness in controlling air pollution, specifically at the local level, have been reported. Adequate technological means are applied considering the source and the nature of the emission as well as its impact on health and the environment. [4]

At this point, international cooperation in terms of research, development, administration policy, monitoring, and politics is vital for effective pollution control. Legislation concerning air pollution must be aligned and updated, and policy makers should propose

the design of a powerful tool of environmental and health protection. As a result, the main proposal of this essay is that we should focus on fostering local structures to promote experience and practice and extrapolate these to the international level through developing effective policies for sustainable management of ecosystems.

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

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ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

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COMPETING INTERESTS

None declared.

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